

Real Time Oil Leakage Detection and Localisation Based on Flow Rates and Echo Principle

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Abstract- This project is primarily designed to ensure real time oil leakage detection and localization using flow rates and echo principles. Flow station A has a microcontroller as the central control unit with start button and flow meter as inputs while time domain reflectometer (TDR), Sound alarm and Pump as outputs. It also has a modem with which it communicates to other flow stations. Flow station B has the same arrangement as flow station A except that it has only sound alarm as its output. Also, the pipeline that links the two flow stations has copper cables aligned along its length so that any attempt to break the pipeline must first cut any of the copper cables which are the basis to detect exact point of leakage using the TDR. Here, fluid flow between two flow stations is considered and the mass flow rates at both ends are measured and compared to check for possible leakage. For a given length of pipeline (L), Cross sectional area (A) and fluid density (ρ) over a given time (t), there is a threshold maximum for mass flow rate difference between flow station A and flow station B. Once, the difference between the two mass flow rates at the two flow stations A and B becomes higher than the given threshold, leakage has occurred, alarm will be activated at both flow stations to alert the workers and the time domain reflectometer (TDR) will be activated at the flow station A. The TDR will send a pulse over the copper cables aligned along the length of the pipeline since for leakage to occur one of the copper cables aligned along the length of the pipeline must have been tampered with. When a pulse is sent across the copper cables, the pulse will be reflected back at a point where the cable is cut. Hence, the TDR measures the time interval between when the pulse is sent to when it was reflected back from the point of leakage as time (t). Then using Echo Equation $V=2X/t$, where V = Velocity of the sent pulse ($3 \times 108\text{m/s}$), hence $X=Vt/2$ where X is the exact point of leakage as measured from flow station A. The developed system recorded a very low error rate of 0.22% with very high precision.

Keywords – Real-time leakage detection, Mass flow rate, Time Domain Reflectometer (TDR), Echo principle, Flow meter.

I. INTRODUCTION

This project is designed with the intention to ensure quick and rapid response to oil leakage so as to avoid environmental degradation and threat to lives brought about by prolonged oil spillage or late detection of oil spillage. Basically, this project was borne out of the need to avoid the repeat of the late detection of oil leakage by shell petroleum development company(SPDC) that led to serious threat and pollution of aquatic and terrestrial environment in Ogoni (a town in Rivers state, Nigeria) as reported by the united nations environment programme (UNEP), in 2011. After careful observation of oil flow from one flow station to another flow station, it was observed that the oil pipelines are checked for possible leakage by the inspection of humans who patrol along the length of the pipelines. However, this technique of human monitoring of pipelines for possible leakages wastes time, energy, money and is untimely which leads to prolonged

leakage before detection. Also, hardware approach like installation of sensors along the length of the pipeline is being employed to replace the human monitoring but any destruction of the sensors by vandals or animals renders this hardware approach useless since leakages would occur without detection. The hardware approach is very expensive since it requires the installation of these expensive sensors along the length of the pipeline and it cannot localise the exact point of leakage, hence, the need for the proposal of timely oil leakage detector and localiser using fluid mechanics and echo principles. With this proposed system, the leakage detection will be fast, timely and quick to avoid prolonged leakage so as to reduce the pollution of the environment [1-3].

1.1 Aim and objectives

The aim of this project is to design a real time oil leakage detector and localiser using fluid mechanics and echo principles. Whereas the objectives are as stated below:

- To design and develop a system that detects oil leakage in real-time using fluid mechanics principle.
- To build a scheme to isolate the point of oil leakage using the echo principle.
- To communicate fault information to where needed for follow up actions.
- To detect oil leakage without incidence of false alarm.

1.2 Significance of the proposed project

Due to the need for timely and early detection of leakage in oil pipeline, the detection method has moved from human inspection to electronic hardware inspection involving remote sensors and now this project would move oil leakage detection to software approach using flow rate differences and equally incorporates oil leakage localiser. Some of the inherent advantages of real time oil leakage detector and localiser using fluid mechanics and echo principles are listed below:

- It saves cost that would have been spent on humans or on digging of trenches to install or repair wireless sensors along the oil pipeline.
- It detects illegal pipe connections inserted along the pipeline which remote sensors and humans cannot detect.
- It is more reliable than remote sensor installations along the pipeline (hardware approach) which when tampered with, by vandals or animals would not detect leakage. However, this project will always detect leakage irrespective of the happenings along the pipeline.

1.3 Scope of the proposed project

This project would develop a test bed to detect pressure drop (flow rate change) due to leakage of fluid in a pipe and to isolate the point of leakage as shown in figures 1.1 and 1.2.

Figure 1.1: Block diagram of flow station A

Figure 1.2: Block Diagram of Flow station B

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Oil exploration includes sum total of all the activities involved in the extracting of crude oil from oil wells for either shipment or refinery. Here, we are much interested on the developmental phases that have occurred in this field for some decades. Oil exploration process in Nigeria started in the late 1960s when crude oil was discovered in commercial quantity in the old eastern region of Nigeria (Now south east and south geopolitical zones in Nigeria). At the inception of this exploration process, most of the works were done by the use of machines and manual sources of labour. As the petroleum industry constantly evolves, the need for fault detection and isolation (FDI) in pipelines becomes more and more important, both to save the environment of possible harm, as well as prevention of economic loss. During the early stage of oil explorations, biological means were used to detect possible leakages along the pipeline. In this biological means, humans were paid to move along the pipelines to report any leakages noticed [4].

However, in the late 90s the oil leakage detection moved from manual to electronic hardware approach which has a number of remote sensors aligned along the length of the pipeline to detect leakages. This later method detects faster than the former but it has some limitations like inability to detect exact point of leakage, low reliability, very expensive, inability to detect illegal tapings on the pipeline and so many others. Hence, the introduction of this project will solve all the shortcomings of electronic hardware approach which is still in use in Nigeria and other oil producing nations of the world. Oil leakages have caused more harm to man and his environment and some instances of documented oil leakages are stated below: The United nations environment programme (UNEP) which indicted Shell petroleum development programme (SDPC) for the deterioration of both aquatic and terrestrial environment in Ogoni, a town in Rivers state, Nigeria due to prolonged unnoticed oil leakage during the 50 years of Shell development Company (SPDC)'s operation in the area. Also in the United states of America, at the end of March 2013, Pegasus had a leak and spilled between 3,500 - 5,000 barrels of crude oil into neighbourhood streets and lawns in Mayflower, Arkansas. Within that same week, Shell had three major oil spills. The last one was in Texas where they estimated that 700 barrels of oil had been lost, amounting to almost 30,000 gallons of crude oil. With the correct model and measurements it may be possible to detect faults like these so that the pipeline can be closed off before it causes too much damage [5 - 8].

Summary of Related Works

A lot of works have been done on oil leakage detection and localisation so as to ensure timely and quick leakage detection and correction. The oil leakage detection started from biological method to the current wireless sensor method with

both still having some serious limitations, hence, the proposal of this project on real time oil leakage detector using fluid mechanics and echo principles.

Biological Detection: In the 70s, when oil pipeline leakage became issue in the oil producing areas (Niger Delta region) of Nigeria due to its attendant pollution, financial losses and degradation of the region, most of the oil giants operating in the region employed hundreds of both the natives and professionals to move along the length of the pipelines on daily basis so as to monitor them and report any leakages noticed along the lengths of the pipelines [8].

Limitations of biological method

Although the biological method provided information about oil pipeline leakages, it has some limitations that made it very unproductive. Such limitations are as stated below:

- Leakage detection was untimely since humans have to move along the lengthy pipeline before they can detect leakages.
- It led to excessive loss of oil products before leakages are detected.
- It led to excessive pollution and degradation of the environment due to late leakage detection.
- It was uneconomical and very expensive since many people were paid to monitor the lengthy pipeline for possible leakages.
- It was unproductive since people assigned to monitor pipeline may not do it often and it could lead to days or weeks of leakages before detection.

2.1.2 Hardware approach using wireless sensors for oil leakage detection: Due to the limitations of the biological method, in the early 2000s, a lot of oil companies started replacing it with wireless sensor detection as shown in figure 2.1 [9 - 12].

Figure 2.1: Schematic diagram of wireless sensor network for leakage detection

Limitations of wireless sensor leakage detection

Although the wireless sensor detection is timely, still in use and more productive than the later but it has some limitations as stated below:

- It cannot determine the exact point of leakage.
- If any of the sensors is damaged by vandals or animals, leakage around the affected area will not be detected.
- It cannot detect any illegal pipe inserted along a pipeline by oil thieves.
- The underground environment imposes major limitations on sensor nodes, such as poor RF transmission and lack of maintainability.
- Digging trenches in order to repair or replace sensor nodes is extremely costly.

Capabilities of the proposed system

Owing to the above enumerated limitations of the wireless sensor leakage detection, there is need to develop a system with the under listed features:

- Ability to timely detect leakage.
- Ability to localise the exact the point of leakage.
- Ability to develop an economical system that can detect leakage without false alarm.
- Ability to detect illegal connection along the oil pipeline by oil thieves.
- Ability to detect leakages irrespective of activities surrounding the pipeline.

Comparison

Hardware based leak detection systems are expensive. To install this kind of hardware along pipelines that expand over hundreds of miles is expensive regardless of where the pipe is situated or what elements it runs through. It also adds more equipment that needs service and repairs. The software based systems usually only need flow, pressure and maybe temperature measurements at the inlet and outlet. If the distribution system is very large with many branches, measurement equipment inside the pipe at certain points is necessary, but it will still be cheaper than the hardware based detection methods [4, 5, 6].

2.4 Time domain reflectometer (TDR)

Time-domain reflectometry (TDR) is a measurement concept that is beginning to find great usefulness in the analysis and synthesis of wideband systems. The art of determining the characteristics of electrical lines by observing reflected waveforms is not new. In fact, power-transmission engineers have located discontinuities in power-transmission systems for many years by monitoring reflections from an electrical pulse. This investigative technique is particularly useful because the amplitude of the reflected signal directly corresponds to the impedance of the discontinuity. Also, the distance to the reflecting impedance can be determined from the time the pulse

takes to return. The limitation of this method is the minimum system rise time. [13].

2.4.1 TDR BASICS: The TDR analysis begins with the propagation of a step or impulse of energy into a system and the subsequent observation, also at the point of insertion, of the energy reflected by the system. Several arrangements are possible, but the following procedure is used by the newer specialized reflectometers. A fast step is developed in a generator that is matched to a 50-ohm line. The incident step passes through a feed-through sampler and is sent into a coax cable that is attached to the circuit element or antenna being tested. The oscilloscope is attached to the feed-through sampler and the incident step, along with the reflected waveform, is displayed on its face. By analyzing the magnitude, duration and shape of the reflected waveform, the nature of the impedance variation in the transmission system can be determined [14, 15].

2.4.2: Leakage-Sensing using TDR: In this project, there is demonstration of a pipeline (Polyethylene, Steel, Cast-iron pipe etc.) network by inserting wires in waterworks pipes and installing exclusive connecting equipment as shown in figure

2.2 . The leakage and breakage are detected by the installed TDR (Time Domain Reflectometer). The sensing wires are generally made of coated copper to transmit electricity [4].

Figure 2.2: Pipeline Structure

III.METHODOLOGY

The proposed Structure basically contains two flow stations as shown in figure 3.1.

This project (Real time oil leakage detector and localiser using fluid mechanics and echo principles) was designed to ensure timely detection and localising of oil leakages in oil pipelines. Hence, the complete work can be seen as a system with two flow stations: Flow stations A and B as shown in figure 3.1. Flow station A has the under listed features:

Figure 3.1: A Sketch of oil flow from flow station A to flow station B

- Microcontroller which does the control and automation.
- Input devices which measure parameters in the flow process. These inputs are flow meter and start button.
- Output devices which act on the flow process. These outputs are sound alarm, pump and time domain reflectometer (TDR)
- Pipeline which serves as the passage or channel of oil flow from flow station A to flow station B. It has wires embedded in its inner walls along the length of the pipeline. It is on these wires that the time domain reflectometer is connected to. Since, the inner walls of the pipeline are covered by wires, hence any leakage along the pipeline would cut the wires and create point of discontinuity for the TDR signal to be reflected back and then used to determine the exact point of leakage using the Echo principle.
- Mobile phone which serves as a modem that receives and sends short message service (SMS) from one flow station to another.

Also, both flow stations A and B have the same arrangement except that the flow station B has sound alarm as the only output device.

The developed system covered the following areas:

- Flow meter measurement
- Flow meters are studied and choice made on the most applicable and available ones. The flow meters were stationed each at flow stations A and B to measure mass flow rates at their respective flow stations. Flow station B receives mass flow rate at point A from flow station A and uses it to compare the mass flow rate at point B. It also uses such comparison to detect whether leakage has occurred or not. According to Continuity equation in fluid mechanics, the flow rate across a channel is constant.

- Analog to digital converter (ADC)
 The flow meter measurements are analog in nature and hence analog to digital conversion is carried out before they are fed to the input of the microcontroller [5, 6, 7, 8].

- Time domain reflectometry
 It is a principle which uses time domain reflectometer to determine the point of leakage on a cable by sending pulses and measuring the time interval between when the pulse is sent and when it is reflected back from the point of breakage or discontinuity [9, 10].

3.1 Proposed Model

Figure 3.2: Pipeline model for leakage detection

Using the structure of pipeline model for leakage detection as shown in figure 3.2 and equations 3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4, 3.5 and 3.6, this research study is explained as follows.

$$M_i = M_o + M_l \quad (3.1)$$

Where,
 M_i = Inlet mass flow rate

M_o = Outlet mass flow rate

M_l = Mass flow rate loss due to the pipeline Length (L), Cross Sectional Area (A), Density of the fluid flowing through the pipeline (ρ) at a given time (t).

$$M_l = LA\rho/t \quad (3.2)$$

$$M_o = M_i + LA\rho/t \quad (3.3)$$

$$M_o - M_i = LA\rho/t \quad (3.4)$$

Hence, for $M_o - M_i \leq LA\rho/t$, it is a normal condition.

However, $M_o - M_i > LA\rho/t$ means that leakage has occurred. NB: For pipeline lengths below 1KM, $M_o - M_i$ is very negligible and is assumed to be zero (Continuity equation).

Once leakage occurs, the time domain reflectometer is activated to determine the time interval between when the pulse is sent and when is received back. Nb: The pipeline to be used here is covered by copper cables running along the length of

the pipeline so that any rupture of the pipeline will first cut any of the copper cables along the length of the pipeline. Hence, once the TDR is activated, it sends pulses along the copper cables along the pipeline and any point where there is leakage, the pulse will be sent back. Then the interval between when the pulse is sent to when the signal is reflected back is measured as time (t).

Figure 3.3: Model for Leakage localisation

Considering the model for leakage localisation as shown in figure 3.3, according to Echo Principle,

$$V = 2X/t \quad (3.5)$$

$$X = Vt/2 \quad (3.6)$$

Where V = Velocity of electromagnetic wave (3×10^8 m/s), X = Leakage distance as measured from Flow Station A and t = time interval between when the pulse is sent to when it is reflected back from the point of leakage.

3.2 Design

Here, top-down design was used. The whole system is broken down into three different smaller modules as shown in figure 3.4[5-8].

MODULE 1: Design of the data acquisition system. This comprises wiring and interconnecting the Flow meters, pump, Sound alarms, modems and relays to the microcontrollers at stations A, B and C as shown in figures 3.5 and 3.6.

MODULE 2: Configuration of the microcontroller and its control software program at flow station A as shown in figure 3.7.

MODULE 3: Configuration of the microcontroller and its control software program at flow stations B as shown in figure 3.8.

Figure 3.4: A modularized approach of the project system design.

Figure 3.7: Control Flowchart at flow station A

Figure 3.5: Circuit diagram of flow station A

Figure 3.8: Control Flowchart at Flow station B

Figure 3.6: Circuit diagram of flow station B

3.3 Implementation.

This work was implemented by the integration of the three design modules discussed in the design of figure 3.4 so as to develop the system in plate 1. Here, the hardware and the

control programme (software) were integrated to achieve the desired results.

Plate 1: The developed system showing the two flow stations and their components

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

For the experiments carried out at the implementation stage of this work, the under listed results in tables 4.1 and 4.2 were obtained for the mass flow rates at flow stations A and B with time interval of 10 minutes. The mass flow rates for flow stations A and B over a given time interval are represented in figures 4.1 and 4.2.

Table 4.1: Mass Flow rates at Flow stations A and B over a given time interval for Length of pipeline = 1m

Mass Flow Rate at Flow Station A (M_A) kg/s	Mass Flow Rate at Flow Station B (M_B) kg/s	Time Interval (Minutes)
10	10	10
10	10	20
10	10	30
10	10	40
10	10	50
10	10	60
10	8	70
6	6	80
4	4	90
2	0	100

Figure 4.1: Mass flow rates of Stations A and B over a given time interval.

For the first experiment, a cut was made on the pipeline to introduce a leak between the 6th and 7th interval, hence, flow station B alerted Flow station A and the later turned off the pump. It took extra 30 minutes for the pipeline content to be emptied as shown in figure 4.1. Also, for the pipeline of length $L = 1m$, the threshold is less than unity and any slight change between the mass flow rates in stations A and B reports leakage as shown in figure 4.1.

Table 4.2: Mass Flow Rates at Flow Stations A and B over a given time interval for $L = 10m$

Mass Flow Rate at Flow Station A (M_A) kg/s	Mass Flow Rate at Flow Station B (M_B) kg/s	Time interval (Minutes)
10	9	10
10	8.5	20
10	8.5	30
10	8	40
10	8	50
10	7.5	60
10	7	70
6	6	80
4	2	90
0	0	100

For the second experiment, a cut was made on the pipeline to introduce a leak between the 6th and 7th interval, hence, flow station B alerted Flow station A and the later turned off the pump. It took extra 30 minutes for the pipeline content to be emptied as shown in figure 4.1. Also, since the length of the pipeline in this experiment has increased to 10m from the initial 1m, it was noticed in figure 4.2 that though the M_A and M_B have some differences, but the flow station B did not alert flow station A about leakage. The threshold of this second

experiment is 2.7kg/s, hence, flow station B only reported leakage when the difference between MA and MB is more than the threshold (2.7kg/s) as shown in figure 4.2 at the 70th minute.

Time in Minutes

Figure 4.2: Mass flow rates of Station A and Station B

Table 4.3: The exact point of leakage and the estimated point of leakage by the Time domain reflectometer (TDR)

Exact point of leakage on the copper cables surrounding the pipeline (m)	Estimated point of leakage as measured by the Time domain reflectometer (TDR) (m)
4.5	4.51
6.5	6.52

Error rate from the above deployed system can be calculated as shown in equation (4).

$$E = \frac{(L_e - L_a) \times 100}{L_a} \quad (4)$$

Where E = Error rate in percentage, L_e = Estimated point of leakage, L_a = Exact point of leakage

From table 4.3, for $L_e = 4.51$, $L_a = 4.52$, $E = \frac{(4.51 - 4.5) \times 100}{4.5}$

$E = 0.22\%$. Hence, the developed model has a very low error rate of 0.22% with very high precision.

From table 4.2, the first reading at flow station B experienced a difference of 1kg/s from the corresponding value at flow station A and subsequent readings had such experience but the leakage alarm was not activated until the difference between them becomes higher than the tolerable threshold $ML = 2.7$. Hence, a change between MA and MB cannot be considered as a leakage until the change becomes higher than the threshold (ML). This slight change was due to losses experienced due to viscosity as the length of the pipeline increased. A leak was introduced between the 6th and 7th interval by giving a cut to the pipeline and the mass flow rate at flow station B became 7kg/s and using $ML = 2.7$ kg/s, the change between MA and MB = 3kg/s which is greater than the ML. Hence, the flow station

B sends an Sms to flow station A that leakage has occurred and the later turned off the pump and turned on the time domain reflectometer (TDR) which immediately sends pulses along the copper cable surrounding the pipeline and the time interval between when the pulse was sent and when it was reflected back due to the cut at the point of leakage was measured as time t and the TDR used it to determine point of leakage as shown in table 4.3. Both MA and MB decreased steadily to zero. Both flow stations also alerted their workers of leakage using sound alarm.

V. CONCLUSION

The above results have shown that this system if implemented in Nigeria's oil and gas industries, will detect oil leakage on real time and also the exact point of leakage since it recorded error rate of 0.22% with very high precision of above 99%. Hence, it would help to reduce the cases of undetected or late detection of oil leakage which is the main cause of pollution in oil producing areas in Nigeria.

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